

Optimizing Design Load Case Reduction for Fatigue Assessment of Mooring Lines in Marine Renewable Energy Systems

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Abstract—The design of ocean renewable energy systems requires extensive fatigue assessments, demanding thousands of simulations and contributing to high computational costs and Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). Climate change further complicates this by altering future marine conditions, making traditional, historical-database-based fatigue analyses potentially unreliable. This study addresses both challenges using K-means clustering and CMIP6 climate projections to reduce the number of metocean conditions analyzed while maintaining accuracy in fatigue damage estimation. Sensitivity analysis confirms that 1000 clusters suffice, reducing cases by 96.57%. Results also show a decline in fatigue damage over the 21st century, underscoring the need for future-aware design practices.

Index Terms—Environmental conditions, clustering techniques, climate models, Design Load Cases (DLCs), fatigue damage, Wave energy converter (WEC) ...

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid integration of renewable energy sources has significantly transformed the global energy landscape in recent years, with wind and solar energy exhibiting particularly robust expansion. In 2022, the installed capacity of these technologies increased by 18.2 % and 8.3 %, respectively, compared to 2021, reaching a cumulative global total exceeding 1,889 GW [1]. Among emerging technologies, Offshore Renewable Energy (ORE) systems—including floating wind, wave, ocean current, and floating solar—are anticipated to play a pivotal role in achieving long-term decarbonization targets. Forecasts indicate that installed offshore capacity could surpass 2,350 GW by 2050 [2]. Nevertheless, offshore systems continue to face substantial obstacles, notably high capital and operational costs, engineering complexity, and environmental limitations, all of which hinder their scalability relative to established onshore wind and photovoltaic solutions. To date, only a few offshore pilot projects have advanced beyond pre-commercial stages (e.g., [3], [4]), underlin-

ing the urgent need for technological innovation to enhance feasibility and competitiveness.

One of the central technical challenges in the development of Marine Renewable Energy (MRE) systems is the accurate representation of environmental loads during the structural design phase. Engineers are required to evaluate a broad set of Design Load Cases (DLCs) to ensure system resilience across a range of operational and extreme metocean scenarios. Standards from regulatory bodies such as the IEC [5] and DNV [6] define procedures for these assessments, emphasizing the integration of wind, wave, current, and sea-level data to replicate site-specific environmental conditions. These DLCs account for:

- **Ultimate loads:** maximum loads that can lead to structural failure.
- **Fatigue loads:** accumulated damage from repeated stresses over time.
- **Serviceability loads:** loads that, while staying within the load capacity, can cause deformations or vibrations that impair functionality.
- **Accidental loads:** loads that the structure must resist to ensure survival in damaged conditions or during unusual events.

Fatigue analysis, in particular, presents a high computational burden due to the need to model the joint probabilistic behaviour of metocean parameters and conduct extensive nonlinear time-domain simulations. Depending on the site, tens of thousands of simulations may be required to achieve statistically robust results [7].

To mitigate this computational expense, recent efforts have focused on reducing the number of environmental conditions considered in long-term fatigue assessments. A common strategy involves selecting the most representative states from historical datasets using clustering-based machine learning algorithms. Prior research has demonstrated the applicability of methods such as K-Means, Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), and the Maximum Dissimilarity Algorithm (MDA) for this purpose. For instance, Camus et al. [8] successfully applied these techniques to cluster wave climate data, finding MDA particularly effective at capturing outlier events with 200 clusters. Kanner et al. [9] later extended MDA to integrate wind data, optimizing results with 2,000 clusters. Saenz-Agirre et al. [10] employed Ward's method to model fatigue for a floating wind turbine using only 20 clusters, signifi-

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cantly streamlining the estimation of equivalent fatigue loads over a projected 30-year operational lifetime.

Despite these advances, the performance of clustering methods has predominantly been evaluated using resource-centric metrics, rather than their accuracy in predicting long-term fatigue damage. This gap was addressed in a more recent study [11], which evaluated clustering methods against actual fatigue performance metrics. Results indicated that the K-Means algorithm achieved convergence in fatigue damage estimates at approximately 1,000 clusters, enabling a 99.62 % reduction in the number of simulation cases required.

It is important to note that previous studies [11] have exclusively relied on historical metocean datasets, consistent with conventional engineering standards, which assume that future conditions will mirror past variability. However, this assumption may no longer hold in light of evolving climate dynamics. Numerous studies have projected substantial changes in offshore wind and wave resources over the 21st century, based on emission scenarios and global climate models from the CMIP6 archive—widely endorsed within the scientific community. Projections for Europe suggest a general decline in wind and wave energy potential, particularly under the high-emission SSP5-8.5 scenario. Additionally, studies such as that of Egor et al. [12] forecast an intensification of extreme weather events in certain regions, such as the Iberian Peninsula, introducing new challenges to structural reliability and design robustness.

Building upon the clustering methodology introduced conceptually in [11] and given this shifting climatological context, the present work extends its application by explicitly incorporating future climate change effects into the fatigue assessment process. This constitutes a key advancement over prior efforts by adapting a resource-based clustering framework to non-stationary environmental conditions. The study evaluates the suitability of the K-Means clustering algorithm not only for its representativeness of offshore energy resources but also for its capability to accurately predict long-term fatigue damage under projected future scenarios. A two-stage methodology is adopted: (1) clustering performance is assessed using traditional resource-based metrics, following the approaches of [8] and [9], and (2) the effectiveness of the reduced condition sets is evaluated through fatigue-specific performance metrics. The case study focuses on a WEC, though the methodology is generalizable to other offshore technologies.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the K-Means clustering methodology and outlines the procedure for fatigue damage evaluation. Section 3 presents the case study, detailing the location, selected ORE technology, and metocean variables, along with the experimental setup used to test clustering effectiveness in condition reduction and fatigue damage estimation. Section 4 summarizes the results, and Section 5 concludes with key findings and implications for future research.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this study is structured into two main phases. The first phase, described in Section II-A, is dedicated to the identification and implementation of a clustering algorithm capable of defining a representative subset of metocean conditions. The second phase, outlined in Section II-B, incorporates these representative conditions into a spectral fatigue analysis framework to estimate fatigue damage. An overview of the complete workflow is illustrated in the block diagram in Figure 1.

A. Clustering technique

This analysis aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of clustering techniques in reducing the computational burden associated with long-term fatigue assessments of ORE systems under future climate conditions. Consistent with prior work presented in [11], the K-Means clustering algorithm has been selected to maintain a standardized basis for comparison.

K-Means partitions a dataset of N observations into K non-overlapping clusters. Each cluster is characterized by its centroid μ_j , which represents the mean of all data points assigned to that cluster. These centroids are not necessarily existing data points but are located within the same feature space.

The algorithm operates iteratively to minimize the Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WCSS)—the cumulative squared Euclidean distance between each data point and the centroid of its respective cluster. This optimization objective is formally defined by Equation 1:

$$\text{WCSS} = \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{x_j \in C_i} \|x_j - \mu_i\|^2, \quad (1)$$

where K is the number of clusters, C_i represents the data points in the i -th cluster, x_i represents a data point in cluster C_i , μ_i is the centroid of the i -th cluster and $\|x_j - \mu_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the data point x_j and the centroid μ_i .

The implementation of the K-Means algorithm is conducted using the Scikit-learn library in Python [13], which provides robust and optimized functions for clustering applications. The algorithm supports manual specification of the number of clusters, enabling sensitivity analyses to determine the optimal cluster count. Furthermore, centroid initialization is handled via the `k-means++` algorithm, which improves upon traditional initialization strategies by maximizing initial inter-centroid distances, thereby reducing the risk of convergence to suboptimal local minima.

The clustering analysis focuses on a WEC technology; therefore, only wave-related environmental parameters are considered. Specifically, the metocean feature space consists of significant wave height (H_s) and spectral peak period (T_p), resulting in a two-dimensional input vector for each of the N samples in the dataset.

To account for projected future environmental variability, wave data spanning the 21st century have been

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the assessment method for K-Means algorithm.

included. However, to preserve temporal resolution and ensure sufficient statistical robustness, the dataset is segmented into three distinct forecast horizons. Each horizon spans at least a decade, as recommended in [38], and includes the following periods: Short - term (2023-2032), Mid - term (2041-2050), Long - term (2091-2100).

Following data collection, a custom-built sensitivity analysis tool is employed to perform an iterative sensitivity analysis on the number of clusters. This tool assesses the internal consistency and structure of the clustered dataset to determine the optimal value of K , ensuring that the reduced set of conditions adequately reflects the underlying variability in wave climate data.

Assessment of the clustering performance is conducted through a set of quantitative indicators aimed at identifying an optimal number of clusters. These metrics characterize the statistical distribution and structure of the metocean dataset and serve to evaluate the quality of the partitioning. The methodology follows the evaluation framework established in previous studies, notably [8] and [9], which have demonstrated the effectiveness of such metrics in environmental data clustering:

- **90th percentile error:** Focuses on the most common environmental conditions, evaluating the accuracy of clustering for values up to the 90th percentile of the dataset.
- **99th percentile error:** Captures the error in the upper tail of the distribution, emphasizing extreme cases.
- **PDF score:** Quantifies discrepancies between the probability distribution functions (PDFs) of the clustered and original data, assessing representativeness [14].

$$PDF_{score} = \sum_{m=1}^M \min(\text{PDF}(y_m^{obs}) - \text{PDF}(y_m^{as})), \quad (2)$$

where M is the number of bins used to represent the PDF.

For each iteration corresponding to a different number of clusters, the selected metrics are computed and recorded. Subsequent analysis involves visual interpretation of these metrics through two-dimensional plots, allowing for the detection of convergence trends and inflection points.

B. Spectral fatigue assessment

In order to evaluate the fatigue life of the system, the centroids derived from the clustering stage are employed as input conditions in a frequency-domain fatigue analysis model, as proposed in [15]. In contrast to conventional time-domain methods—which typically rely on rainflow counting—spectral approaches significantly reduce computational cost while preserving a high degree of accuracy. This makes them especially suitable for applications involving large sets of environmental scenarios.

Consistent with the benchmarking study conducted by Eguzkine *et al.* [15], the Tovo-Benasciutti spectral method is adopted in this study to estimate the cumulative fatigue damage in the mooring lines of the WEC system. This method has demonstrated superior performance compared to the Dual Narrow-Banded (DNB) approach traditionally recommended in DNVGL-OS-E301 [6].

The analysis begins by reconstructing irregular sea states from the metocean parameters H_s and T_p using the JONSWAP wave spectrum formulation. A peak enhancement factor of 3.3 is applied, following established practice. For simplicity, the mean wave direction is omitted in this study, as its influence on fatigue response is considered secondary for the scope of the analysis.

To ensure the dynamic characteristics of the system are adequately captured, the IEC 61400 standard [5] specifies that time series representing operational wave conditions must span a minimum duration of 10 minutes. However, in alignment with the methodology in [15], this duration has been extended to 125 minutes

in the present study to enhance the consistency and robustness of fatigue estimations. For each metocean condition (i.e., each centroid), at least six independent realizations (random seeds) are generated to account for stochastic variability and ensure statistical reliability of the results.

These wave time series are then transformed into synthetic stress histories using hydrodynamic simulations of the reference WEC system described in Section III-B. Specifically, stress responses in the mooring lines are derived from simulations conducted with WEC-Sim, a time-domain modelling tool tailored for wave energy converters. This approach circumvents the need for conducting full-scale simulations for every individual sea state, thus significantly reducing the computational burden while maintaining fidelity to the system’s hydrodynamic behaviour.

The final stage involves applying the spectral model to estimate the fatigue damage accumulation rate associated with each centroid. This enables a systematic evaluation of how the predicted fatigue damage varies with the number of clusters used. In doing so, the methodology supports the identification of a minimum yet sufficient number of clusters capable of accurately representing long-term fatigue behaviour over the system’s operational life cycle.

III. CASE STUDY

The analysis utilizes metocean data from a geographically defined site, as described in Section III-A, to investigate the applicability of clustering algorithms under realistic environmental conditions. A comprehensive future long-term fatigue assessment is performed using the wave energy converter introduced in Section III-B, which serves as the reference system for this study.

In addition, the experimental scenarios detailed in Section IV are employed to evaluate the extent to which clustering techniques can reduce the dimensionality of the future environmental input space. This evaluation focuses on maintaining the accuracy of fatigue damage predictions while significantly decreasing the number of simulated metocean conditions.

A. Location and wave data

This analysis is centred on the maritime region of the Bay of Biscay, with a particular focus on the Biscay Marine Energy Platform (BIMEP), located approximately 1.5 km offshore near the town of Armintza. The site lies within a bathymetric range of 50 to 90 meters (see Figure 2) and is situated off the Basque coastline. Recognized as a dedicated test facility for marine energy converters, BIMEP offers an ideal environment for evaluating the effectiveness of clustering techniques in long-term fatigue analysis. Its geographic positioning exposes it to a broad spectrum of metocean conditions, providing a robust basis for testing the generalizability and reliability of data reduction methods under real-world scenarios.

The facility’s operational infrastructure, coupled with the availability of high-resolution environmental

Fig. 2: Metocean data acquisition area at the BIMEP location.

datasets, makes it a valuable resource for validating methodological approaches in the context of ORE. As a result, BIMEP is particularly well suited for assessing the performance of clustering algorithms in fatigue-oriented design applications.

Environmental data employed in this study are sourced from the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), which provides projections of future wave climate conditions derived from the WaveWatch III numerical model driven by outputs from the CMIP6 global climate model ensemble. Specifically, the dataset used here is based on simulations from the EC-Earth3 GCM using a CD-FAC scaling parameter of 1.0, as recommended in prior research [12]. In order to assess the impact of future climate variability, the analysis adopts the SSP5-8.5 scenario—representing the highest-emission pathway within the CMIP6 framework. The dataset includes H_s and T_p wave parameters. These are provided at a temporal resolution of 3 hours and a spatial resolution of 0.5° . The coordinate closest to BIMEP (43.5°N , 3.0°W) is selected for data extraction.

Fig. 3: Metocean variables distribution for each projected horizon.

Following established methodologies [12], wave climate projections are extracted for three forecast horizons, each spanning a minimum of 10 years. These periods are intended to reflect short-, mid-, and long-term future scenarios. The extracted metocean variables H_s

and T_p are used to construct joint probability scatter diagrams, which highlight regions of highest frequency occurrence and delineate extreme event boundaries.

Discrepancies are observed in the distribution and frequency of sea states associated with each future horizon. For instance, sea states corresponding to the near-term period exhibit a more compact spread, with H_s values not exceeding 7.5 meters. In contrast, the mid-term and long-term horizons show the emergence of more energetic and extreme conditions, with H_s values reaching up to 8–9 meters. Moreover, the occurrence patterns of H_s and T_p also display notable variations across horizons. In the long-term scenario, for example, there is an increasing prevalence of lower-energy sea states.

To validate these observations, a post-processing analysis of the metocean dataset was conducted, focusing on the evolution of both typical and extreme conditions. The median values of H_s and T_p were computed for each horizon to represent central tendencies, while the 99.9th percentile was used to characterize extreme events. A summary of these results is presented in Table I.

TABLE I: Projected mean and extreme metocean conditions at BIMEP for near-, mid-, and long-term horizons.

Forecasting horizon	Mean conditions		Extreme conditions	
	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]
Near term	1.17	11.49	6.28	20.40
Mid term	1.08	11.36	6.97	20.74
Long term	1.00	10.86	6.39	20.40

Based on the data in Table I, it can be confirmed that throughout the 21st century, metocean conditions at the BIMEP site exhibit a progressive decline in average sea state energy. Simultaneously, an intensification of extreme sea states is evident, particularly pronounced during the mid-term horizon.

B. Wave energy converter: RM3

This study employs a WEC of the point absorber type as the reference system for fatigue analysis, specifically the Reference Model 3 (RM3) developed by Sandia National Laboratories. This well-established benchmark model is widely used for simulation-based research in wave energy applications.

The RM3 configuration comprises a toroidal floating body connected to a submerged reaction plate by means of a vertical spar, as depicted in Figure 4. Station-keeping is achieved through three mooring lines anchored to the seabed. From a hydrodynamic perspective, the system predominantly operates in heave motion, oscillating vertically in response to wave excitation forces. The submerged reaction plate acts to resist motion, thereby increasing the relative displacement between the floater and the wave surface, which enhances power absorption efficiency.

Detailed geometric dimensions and physical properties of the RM3 device are summarized in Table II, providing a comprehensive basis for the structural and fatigue analysis performed in this work.

TABLE II: Technical specifications of the reference RM3 model [15].

Parameter	Units	Value
Floater mass	kg	$7.27 \cdot 10^5$
Submerged buoy mass	kg	16755
Floater inertia	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$	
	Ixx	20907301
	Iyy	21306091
	Izz	37085481
Spar inertia	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$	
	Ixx	94419615
	Iyy	94407091
	Izz	28542225
Chain Nominal Diameter	mm	144
S1 length	m	40
S2 length	m	240
Linear density	kg/m	126
Line stiffness (EA)	N	$583.38 \cdot 10^6$

Fig. 4: Representation of the standard RM3 WEC and mooring setup [15].

IV. TEST CASES

A multi-stage testing framework has been designed to evaluate the effectiveness of the K-Means clustering algorithm in both simplifying future metocean condition datasets and preserving the accuracy of cumulative fatigue damage estimation.

The first stage, described in Section IV-A, focuses on verifying the algorithm's capacity to capture key resource characteristics, including dominant sea states and extreme events. The final stage, detailed in Section IV-B, addresses the algorithm's reliability in approximating long-term fatigue damage under reduced condition sets.

A. Metocean-based analysis

After applying K-Means, the derived centroids are analysed for their ability to accurately represent critical features of the metocean environment. Specifically, metrics such as the 90th percentile is employed to assess the algorithm's effectiveness in capturing frequently occurring conditions that are most influential in fatigue accumulation. In parallel, the 99th percentile is used to evaluate how well extreme wave conditions are represented. Additionally, the PDF_{score} is introduced to quantify the degree to which the full statistical distribution of environmental conditions is preserved. Each of these performance indicators is plotted as a

function of the number of clusters, enabling visual identification of convergence trends and determination of an optimal cluster count.

B. Damage-based analysis

In parallel with the resource-based evaluations, a sensitivity study is also performed to examine how the number of clusters affects the accuracy of fatigue damage predictions. For each tested cluster count, centroids are generated and applied as input conditions in a spectral fatigue model based on the Tovo–Benasciutti formulation.

The average fatigue damage corresponding to each cluster configuration is then computed, allowing for the construction of a damage convergence curve. This curve serves to identify the threshold beyond which increasing the number of clusters yields diminishing returns in damage prediction accuracy, thereby supporting the selection of a computationally efficient yet reliable clustering resolution.

V. RESULTS

The outcome of the analysis is structured to assess two main aspects: the capability of clustering algorithms to minimize the complexity of environmental datasets, and the influence of this reduction on the accuracy of long-term fatigue damage estimations. The findings are presented across three dedicated subsections: V-A and V-B.

A. Metocean-based DLC reduction

Building upon the verification procedures described in Section IV, the first set of results focuses on assessing the clustering algorithm’s capability to represent most frequent, moderate and extreme sea states. The evaluation emphasizes the degree to which clustered data can reproduce key statistical characteristics of the wave climate.

A preliminary step involves quantifying the error in the 90th and 99th percentiles of H_s , a primary descriptor of wave climate variability (refer to Figure 5). Results shown in Figure 5a indicate that increasing the number of clusters leads to a marked reduction in the 90th percentile error, thereby improving the representation of frequently occurring sea states.

While the 90th and 99th percentile error metrics provide insight into specific segments of the wave height distribution, they offer only a partial view of the clustering performance. To complement this analysis and capture the overall distributional fidelity, the PDF score metric is introduced. This score enables a quantitative comparison between the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the original metocean dataset and the clustered representation.

As shown in Figure 6, clustering configurations with fewer than 600 centroids exhibit poor agreement with the original data distribution. A noticeable improvement is observed with increasing cluster numbers, with PDF_{score} values reaching acceptable levels beyond 4,000 clusters. Nonetheless, complete convergence of

(a) 90th percentile error of H_s .

(b) 99th percentile error of H_s .

Fig. 5: Sensitivity analysis of resource based metrics respect to the number of clusters.

Fig. 6: Sensitivity analysis of the PDF_{score} .

the metric is not achieved, even at 5,000 clusters, suggesting persistent discrepancies in representing the full statistical structure.

Additionally, the results indicate that the long-term

forecast horizon yields comparatively lower PDF_{score} values. This behaviour may be attributed to a greater dispersion of sea states in this period, presenting a more complex and heterogeneous dataset that challenges the K-Means algorithm's ability to capture the full extent of variability.

B. Damage-based DLC reduction

This section consolidates the key findings from the fatigue analysis conducted on the RM3 point absorber, with a focus on the accumulated fatigue damage in the bolted connections of the mooring system.

As outlined in earlier sections, the fatigue estimation methodology is based on the Tovo–Benasciutti spectral approach, utilizing synthetic tension time series generated according to the procedure in [15]. These time series simulate dynamic loads on the mooring system resulting from the hydrodynamic response of the RM3 device under varying sea states.

The total tension in each mooring line is modelled as the superposition of two components [15]:

- A wave-frequency (WF) component: captures short-period, high-frequency oscillations induced by surface wave motion
- A low-frequency (LF) component: reflects slower stress variations associated with environmental forces such as tidal flows and steady currents.

These tension components are computed for each representative sea state, as defined by the centroids obtained through clustering. For each centroid, six independent 7,500-second simulations are generated to ensure statistical robustness. This process is repeated across all iterations of the sensitivity analysis, which varies the number of clusters. For example, an iteration with 50 clusters results in a total of 300 synthetic signals (i.e., 6 realizations per centroid).

After the generation of synthetic loads, the spectral model is applied to compute the mean fatigue damage corresponding to each iteration. The damage trends across different cluster resolutions are presented in Figure 7, offering insight into the convergence behavior of the clustering-based reduction method.

Fig. 7: Evolution of means damage as a function of cluster number

Figure 7 further demonstrates that mean fatigue damage exhibits significant variability at lower cluster

counts; however, from approximately 1,000 clusters onward, the damage estimates stabilize consistently across all three future time horizons. This stabilization indicates that a clustering resolution of 1,000 centroids is sufficient to reliably estimate cumulative fatigue damage. As a result, the number of environmental conditions required for the fatigue analysis is drastically reduced—from nearly 30,000 samples (based on 10 years of 3-hourly data) to only 1,000 representative sea states.

A clear downward trend in fatigue damage is also observed when progressing through the future projection horizons, with the lowest damage values appearing in the long-term period. This trend reflects anticipated shifts in sea state distributions due to climate change. Specifically, as highlighted in study [12], the Iberian Peninsula is expected to experience a decline in average wave energy resource over the 21st century. Since fatigue accumulation is primarily driven by the most frequently occurring wave conditions, this reduction in wave energy directly correlates with lower fatigue demands.

Additionally, the results suggest that under the projected sea states for each 10-year horizon, the RM3 device's mooring system is not expected to reach fatigue failure. The mean cumulative damage remains well below unity, indicating that the structure retains an adequate safety margin with respect to fatigue, and confirming its durability under the simulated environmental conditions.

VI. CONCLUSION

In order to address emerging challenges in the ORE sector, this study presents a computationally efficient methodology designed to streamline the fatigue design workflow under evolving wave climate conditions. Unlike previous approaches such as [11], which rely exclusively on historical metocean data, the proposed method incorporates projected wave climate scenarios derived from CMIP6 global models. This enables the integration of non-stationary resource variability into established design practices governed by DNV and IEC standards. By mitigating the high computational demands typically associated with long-term fatigue analysis—particularly in the context of DLC 1.2—the proposed framework offers a scalable and climate-aware solution for enhancing the structural reliability of ORE technologies under evolving environmental forcing.

The application of K-Means clustering algorithm technique have demonstrated a significant reduction in the dimensionality of metocean datasets used for design, while preserving the statistical representation of both dominant and extreme environmental conditions across future climate scenarios. The results indicate that employing 2,000 clusters allows for accurate characterization of the most frequently occurring sea states, as well as rare, high-impact events, with negligible error margins.

Furthermore, the fidelity of clustering methods in estimating cumulative fatigue damage has been validated. Findings reveal that 1,000 clusters are sufficient

to replicate the full-spectrum, long-term fatigue behaviour of ORE structures, leading to a 96.57 % reduction in the total number of simulation cases—thereby substantially lowering the computational resources required for large-scale fatigue assessments.

Beyond the efficiency gains, this research underscores the critical role of incorporating future metocean projections into structural design practices. Given the strong coupling between climate change and fatigue performance, the observed trend of decreasing fatigue damage throughout the 21st century suggests that conventional design methodologies should be revised to reflect changing environmental conditions and resource availability.

REFERENCES

- [1] IRENA, “RENEWABLE ENERGY STATISTICS 2023,” International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, Tech. Rep., 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.irena.org/Publications/2023/Mar/Renewable-capacity-statistics-2023?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- [2] —, “Offshore Renewables: An Action Agenda for Deployment,” International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, Tech. Rep., 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.irena.org/publications/2021/Jul/Offshore-Renewables-An-Action-Agenda-for-Deployment?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- [3] Equinor, “Hywind tampen,” Online, 2024, last accessed: 29/09/2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.equinor.com/energy/hywind-tampen>
- [4] P. G. Large, “Provence grand large,” Online, 2024, last accessed: 29/09/2024. [Online]. Available: <https://provencegrandlarge.fr/>
- [5] I. E. C. (IEC), “Une-en iec 61400-1:2020: Wind turbines – part 1: Design requirements,” Standard, 2020, spanish version of IEC 61400-1:2020, Published by UNE.
- [6] D. GL, “Dnv-st-0119 floating wind turbine structures,” 2021, edition July 2021.
- [7] G. Katsikogiannis, “Estimation of long-term fatigue and extreme responses of large-diameter monopiles for offshore wind turbines,” Ph.D. dissertation, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway, 2024, PhD dissertation, Department of Marine Technology. [Online]. Available: <https://ntnuopen.ntnu.no/ntnu-xmlui/handle/11250/3116766>
- [8] P. Camus, F. J. Mendez, R. Medina, and A. S. Cofiño, “Analysis of clustering and selection algorithms for the study of multivariate wave climate,” vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 453–462. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0378383911000354>
- [9] S. Kanner, A. Aubault, A. Peiffer, and B. Yu, “Maximum dissimilarity-based algorithm for discretization of metocean data into clusters of arbitrary size and dimension,” *Proceedings of the International Conference on Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering - OMAE*, vol. 10, pp. 1–9, 2018.
- [10] A. Saenz-Aguirre, A. Ulazia, G. Ibarra-Berastegi, and J. Saenz, “Floating wind turbine energy and fatigue loads estimation according to climate period scaled wind and waves,” vol. 271, p. 116303. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0196890422010810>
- [11] A. Martinez-Perurena, E. Martinez-Puente, I. Llavori, M. Penalba, and G. Iglesias, “On the reduction of design load cases for fatigue assessment of mooring lines for offshore renewable energy systems,” in *Proceedings of the ASME 2025 44th International CONFERENCE ON OCEAN, OFFSHORE AND ARTIC ENGINEERING*, 2025.
- [12] E. Barkanov, M. Penalba, A. Martínez, A. Martinez-Perurena, A. Zarketa-Astigarraga, and G. Iglesias, “Evolution of the european offshore renewable energy resource under multiple climate change scenarios and forecasting horizons via cimp6,” *Energy Conversion and Management*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:266808316>
- [13] scikit-learn developers, “Clustering,” Online, 2024, last accessed: 29/09/2024. [Online]. Available: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/clustering.html>
- [14] M. Penalba, C. Guo, A. Zarketa-Astigarraga, G. Cervelli, G. Giorgi, and B. Robertson, “Bias correction techniques for uncertainty reduction of long-term metocean data for ocean renewable energy systems,” *Renewable Energy*, vol. 219, p. 119404, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148123013198>
- [15] E. Martinez-Puente, A. Zarketa-Astigarraga, M. Martinez-Agirre, A. Zabala, J. A. Esnaola, M. Muñoz-Calvente, I. Llavori, and M. Penalba, “Benchmarking of spectral methods for fatigue assessment of mooring systems and dynamic cables in offshore renewable energy technologies,” *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 308, p. 118311, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029801824016494>